

FDM4Ing Community Meeting CC-42: Introduction in RDM and using RDMO for your engineering projects

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Abstract

The FDM4Ing CC-42 Community Meeting 2023's RDMO workshop, held online on October 27 with 30 participants exploring and discussing RDMO's applicability, benefits, and drawbacks for research data management (RDM) in engineering projects.

1. Introduction

This RDMO workshop as part of the FDM4Ing CC-42 Community Meeting 2023 took place online on 27 October 2023 with around 30 participants, including professors, postdocs, doctoral students, librarians, infrastructure employees, and employees in non-university research institutions. After an introduction to RDM by Canan Hastik, Jürgen Windeck presented the relevance of data management plans (DMPs) using the NFDI4Ing RDMO tool (RDMO, 2023). In the following interactive workshop session, Philipp Wetterich, Maximilian Kuhr, Manuel Rexer, and Michael Frank from the Department of Mechanical Engineering at the Technical University of Darmstadt presented their research projects in a short impulse talk. These are either in the conceptualisation phase, in the approval phase, or about to start funding. All projects are strongly application-orientated, industry-related, location-based or supra-regional, and building on complex data acquisition processes, analysis, and processing chains. These projects served as case studies in the three breakout sessions moderated by Jürgen Windeck, Sabine Schönau and Canan Hastik, in which the applicability of RDMO was discussed along with its advantages and disadvantages.

2. FDM in a Nutshell

In research projects in general and within Community Cluster CC-42, the understanding of what research data is seems quite diverse and ranges from simulation data, experimental data to transient sensor measurements, measurement data from kinetic models, or measurement series but also standards, regulations, raw data from databases, machine-readable data sheets, survey data, image, AV and CT data, microscopy images, AI models, infrastructure topologies, to name just a few (c.f. the term ‘research data’ in the DFG checklist and the guidelines for handling research data (DFG, 2021)). Basically “digital research data is [...] all available digital data that is created during the research process or is the result of it and research data management (RDM) includes all activities related to processing, storage, archiving, and publication of research data (Kindinger and Schirmbacher, 2013).” RDM process usually known as the research data life cycle supports the correct handling of research data which is one of the most important prerequisites for scientific activities to ensure compliance with good scientific practice. The prerequisite for this is professional handling of research data throughout the stages of the data life cycle. And this is where the data management plan comes into play.

3. Introduction to DMPs and RDMO

DMPs support the planning process to improve the reusability and quality of research data. Based on DMP templates researchers are guided through a list of topics that need to be considered in RDM. For the engineering community Base Service S1 provides RDMO, an open source DMP tool widely established in Germany and adapted for the engineering community. The NFDI4Ing template relates to data usage, documentation and data quality, storage and technical backup during the course of the project, legal aspect, data exchange and permanent accessibility of data, as well as responsibilities and resources.

By applying RDMO to the three specific use cases, the workshop offered a great chance to talk about requirements of CC-42, and needs depending on different levels of knowledge and experience. Since not only the experience and knowledge of RDM as well as the needs varied greatly in the three projects and groups, the feedback was highly subjective and individual. Some junior researchers require more detailed information and an overview while more experienced researchers focus on supporting the upcoming grant application and vice versa. Particularly for the project in the pre-application phase, the tenor towards RDMO and the template was clear: the questions from the template were still too specific for this point in time. General questions with more extensive help texts and more links to good examples were required. An overview of all subject-specific offerings at the NFDI4Ing was also desired. From RDMO, the participants would have liked the output of the answers to be available in a more usable form for the application. In any case, it turned out that, especially in the context of industry corporations, additional support with regard to cooperative data use, anonymization and pseudonymization of data and processes is needed and should be implemented. Furthermore, connecting the described data sets to visualize the data workflow of a project and its context was suggested.

To further improve the RDMO service, the community requested best practice examples and user stories to support filling out the templates. This leads us to launch a call to the data management experts in the NFDI4Ing community to provide the RDMO team with good examples and answers that make the description categories better understandable, e.g. "Please do not use proprietary data in a specific file format that comes from a machine but save the data in HDF5."

4. Using RDMO for engineering projects

The relevance of good research data management is still largely dictated by research funders. The fact that good handling of one's own data can help researchers to work effectively with their data beyond the project is only slowly becoming apparent to them. The community particularly sees the benefits in 'controlling the chaos', traceability, transparency, sharing data, reproducibility, reuse, project management support, sustainability of the use of funds, error prevention and avoiding misunderstandings, legal certainty, ensure trust in results, optimization of data quality, clear referencing, dialogue nationally, internationally and across subject boundaries, fusion of model and data to reduce uncertainty, and to ensure sovereignty of research because data is power. However, the misconception persists that filling out data management plans represents an additional burden. The individual groups within the NFDI4Ing try in various ways to provide researchers with tools to facilitate the process of rethinking - through interdisciplinary services such as helpdesks, infrastructures such as RDMO in this case, or subject-specific help texts and explanations, as in the NFDI4Ing-template, that can be used in RDMO. In this context, the FAIR principles, see also 'The FAIR Cookbook' (ELIXIR, 2023) or 'How to FAIR' (Deutz et al., 2020), represent the core building blocks for good RDM.

5. Lessons Learned

Since in Germany there are usually only basic personal obligations, such as guidelines for good scientific practice or principles of open access, but there are hardly any detailed requirements, it is

all the more important to know the RDM policies in the current funding programs. When planning a project, it should be considered whether and which data resulting from a project are relevant for other contexts and in what way the data can be made available for subsequent use. Therefore, data must be documented, long-term secured, made available, and permanently accessible according to standards and by respecting third-party rights.

Since the handling of research data, as we saw very well in this workshop, is largely influenced by the working methods in scientific disciplines and individual project contexts, the German Research Foundation calls on disciplines, professional societies and communities to reflect on their handling of research data to develop appropriate guidelines for the discipline-specific use and, if necessary, open provision of research data, e.g. “recommendations for dealing with research data from Expert Forum Materials Science and Engineering” (DFG, 2023).

The valuable insights gained in this workshop can be summarised as follows. While enquiries from researchers about RDMO are usually very abstract, these three case studies and the direct project reference in each case offered great added value for RDM advisors. As the requirements for RDM differ for projects in the conception and proposal phase, RDMO should act as a generic guidance tool as well as a specific project management tool with granular descriptions modularly. While RDMO already provides a feature to export the DMP, optimized support for the application process is desired. Unfortunately, aspects that are relevant for industrial collaboration are underrepresented in RDMO.

This workshop thus laid the foundation for an application-related harmonization and standardization of the use of DMPs in CC-42. By adding further best practice examples from the entire NFDI4ing community to the questionnaire in the RDMO templates, this process can be continued and further expanded. So, please provide the RDMO team of S1 with your examples!

6. References

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